

DISASTER MANAGEMENT

Asharani.C

Assistant Professor,

Government First Grade College Nelamangala

Bangalore Rural Karnataka, India

Abstract:

A Disaster is any tragic event occurring from earth quake, floods, accidents, fire or explosions and disturbs the working of a society and can bring heavy losses to the men, material and environment.

Disaster can be both manmade and natural made .Man made are fire, accidents or explosions where as natural made is earth quake, floods volcano. Prevention is possible in manmade disaster and some natural disaster .Disaster management will not completely eliminate the threat nor does take out the danger rather try to reduce the impact of its seriousness. Disaster management is how we handle human, material, environment, it is the system of how we train ourselves, react it and learn from its effects of failure.

Disaster management can work effectively only when peoples and government work together which is the government has to frame measures to reduce the impact of disaster. Proper disaster management is when we create awareness among the people precautionary measure to handle during emergency situation .The Government of India proceeds from the conviction that development cannot be maintained unless disaster mitigation is built in to the development process. Disasters .In disaster management there need 3Ps to work which helps us to give good results and they are. Prevention, Preparation and Possession regaining. Mainly in case of natural disaster more interest ,care and measure has to be taken as it is un controllable factor and it is not in our hand to control .How much ever the latest technology is introduced whatever modern we are if we are unable to maintain the balance we will face a disaster . So proper balance has to be maintained. This paper highlights about Disaster management in India and helps us to know Disaster management in vast.

Key words: Mitigation, Government, Environment, Preparation

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Introduction

India is a land of “Unity in Diversity”. It is land with large rivers, vast seas, high mountains ranges, dense forest, sandy deserts, countless rivers and streams. It has a climate consists of different range of weather conditions, different topography. India has a unique Geo climate

Conditions. Floods, droughts, cyclons, earthquakes, Tsunami. India is prone to most disaster in South Asia and world.

Disaster is a event which is very serious and causes disturbance in society. It is a sudden event bringing great change, loss and destruction to life and property and these loss and damages cannot be measured .Disaster has covered with 3Us

1) Unpredictable 2) Unfamiliarity 3) Uncertainty

According to United Nations Office for Disaster risk reduction Some 79,732 people have lost their lives and 108 crore people were affected in 321 incidents of natural disaster in India.

Disaster

Meaning:

The word 'disaster' is derived from the 16th century word 'desastre'. The word is the combination of two Latin words - 'Dis' and 'Astro' means bad star. Therefore, disaster can be simply referred to as the unforeseen calamities caused by planetary

The term “Disaster” has been defined in many terms „disaster “has certain allied words, such as extreme events, hazards, vulnerability, Hazard is a dangerous phenomenon,

A hazard is any object, situation, or behaviour that has the potential to cause injury, ill health, or damage to property or the environment.

Vulnerability is the inability to overcome a hazard or to respond when a disaster has occurred.

Types of Disaster

- Natural disaster
- Manmade disaster

Natural Disaster is naturally occurring physical phenomena caused naturally or either by rapid or slow on set events which are

Geophysical - Earth quakes, tsunami, and volcano.

Hydrological –Floods

Meteorological- cyclones, storms

Biological-disease epidemic, insects and animal plagues.

Man-made disaster are those disaster which is manmade like emergencies, conflicts, famine Industrial accidents and transport accidents these are events that are not natural but damaged by human beings

Disaster Management

Disaster management occupies an, main place in this country's policy framework as it is the poor and the under-privileged who are worst affected on account of calamities /disasters.

Disaster Management is a strategic planning and procedure that is administered and employed to protect from severe damages when natural or human made calamities and catastrophic event occur.

According to The UNISDR defines disaster risk management as the systematic process of using administrative decisions, organization, operational skills and capacities to implement policies, strategies and coping capacities of the society and communities to lessen the impacts of natural hazards and related environmental and technological disasters.

Disaster Management Act, 2005

This has been enacted as the central Act to deal with the management of disasters. This act has a three tier Disaster Management structure in India at National, States and District levels. It puts down institutional and coordination for effective Disaster Management (DM) at the national, state, district and local levels. As mandatory by this Act, the Government of India framed a multi-tiered institutional system consisting of the National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) headed by the Prime Minister, State Disaster Management Authorities (SDMAs) headed by the Chief Ministers District Disaster Management Authorities (DDMAs) headed by the District Collectors
National Disaster Management Authority

The Disaster Management Act of the Central Government establishes NDMA.

The head will be prime minister as nodal authority and chairperson.

It will have maximum of nine members nominated by chairman which is Prime Minister.

Power and functions of NDMA

- Laying down the policies, plans and guidelines for disaster management
- Ensuring timely and effective response to disaster.
- It lays down the policies on disaster management,
- Approve the national plan, and approve plans developed by various ministries of the union,
- Lay down the guidelines to be followed by the state authorities in drawing up state plans.

National Executive Committee

Apart from NDMA, the central government also constitutes a National Executive Committee which is responsible for assisting NDMA in execution of various functions for disaster management. The secretary of the ministry which is responsible for disaster management is chairperson of NEC.

Powers and Functions of NEC

- Help NDMA in its functions
- Implementing the plans and policies of NDMA
- Ensuring compliance with the directives of Central Government.
- To act as a coordinating and monitoring body for disaster management
- Prepare the National Plan to be approved by the NDMA

State Disaster Management Authority

A state Disaster Management Authority is to be established in every state government. The Chief Minister of the state is the chairperson of SDMA. There are maximum 9 members other than the chairperson.

Powers and Functions of SDMA

- To put down the disaster management policies and plans for state
- To lay down state disaster management policy
- To get approve of state plans as per guidelines of national plans.
- To put down guidelines to be followed by departments of the state.

State Executive Committee

The state government also creates a State Executive Committee to assist the State Authority in the performing of its functions and to coordinate the action in according with the guidelines laid down by the State Authority.

Its powers and functions are almost the same as of the NEC in state level.

District Disaster Management Authority

The DDMA are set up by state government. It consists of Chairperson and seven members. The collector or District Magistrate or Deputy Commissioner will be the chairman.

Powers and Functions of DDMA

The DDMA works as a district planning, coordinating and implementing body for disaster management.

It will coordinate with the upper two tiers of the structure

It will plan the implementation of the prevention, mitigation and preparedness at local level

A Disaster Management Plan in India includes the following:-

1. Institutional and policy framework
2. Early warning system
3. Disaster prevention and mitigation

National Crisis Management Committee (NCMC).

Crisis Management Group

Control Room (Emergency Operation Room).

Contingency Action Plan

State Relief Manuals Funding mechanisms

National Crisis Management Committee (NCMCC)

The head of the NCMC is Cabinet secretary .Members of all concerned ministries Departments and organisations will be the members of the committee .The NCMC can also give direction to the crisis management group.

Crisis Management Group (CMP)

The chairman of the CMG will be the Central Relief Commissioner in the Ministry of Home Affairs. It has Nodal officers who will be senior officers .Their function is to review every year contingency plans, and measures to be taken for handling it. Also coordinate various activities of the central government and State Government.

Contingency Action plan :(CAP)

CAP identifies where natural disaster occurred and takes steps and these initiatives are taken by various central Ministries and department.

State Relief Manuals (SRM)

Manuals is book which guides .And every state will have a State Relief manuals which

tells the role of each officer in the state to be performed.

National Disaster Management Plan (NDMP), 2016 is the first national plan prepared in the country for the disaster management. With National Disaster Management Plan 2016. India has joined our National Plan with the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030, to which India is a signatory.

Recommendations:

People plays a very important role in reducing the vulnerability in each stage and it is possible by educating them about disaster management and training them to handle during disaster. India has taken good step by education from in school which help them to train and handle disaster from their school age. Good coordination and strict rules is very important in reducing vulnerability which can help in disaster preparedness and response. We can provide trained manpower by giving training to informal groups .

Conclusion:

Natural hazards are result of climatic imbalance it cannot be controlled by us but by conducting awareness campaign and by developing effective warning system it can be prevented. Along with government department, various departments and people together should work together to reduce the vulnerability. Communities overpowered by a major disaster such as earthquake, flood or fire etc, usually require long-term help from national or international levels to overcome and regain their normal lives. Introducing the disaster-prone community to practical disaster preparedness activities can build their capacity and confidence and to cope with future disasters. This can be done by analysing past experiences, conducting risk assessments and creating disaster preparedness plans. Both

Reference

1. An overview of Disaster Management in India – A.J. SHAH
2. Disaster Management in India –Indian Research Journal of Extension Education
3. <https://www.unisdr.org>